

Nuclear observations to improve Climate research and GHG emission estimates

Ambient gamma dose rate modelling

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Gamma dose rate measurements are essential for quantifying variations in environmental radiation and for understanding the processes that influence background radiation levels. Continuous monitoring of the gamma dose rate provides a direct indicator of changes in ambient gamma radiation resulting from natural radionuclides present in the atmosphere and deposited on the ground.

One of the primary contributors to short-term fluctuations in environmental gamma radiation is the behaviour of radon (^{222}Rn) and its short-lived progeny (such as ^{214}Pb and ^{214}Bi). During precipitation events, these radon progeny are efficiently scavenged from the atmosphere by raindrops and transported to the ground surface. This process leads to a temporary increase in gamma radiation at ground level, because these radionuclides emit penetrating gamma rays during their decay. As a result, rainfall events are often associated with measurable enhancements in the gamma dose rate.

Developing a model that describes the increase in gamma dose rate during rainfall events requires reliable gamma dose measurements as an observable parameter. The gamma dose rate serves as an integrated radiological quantity that reflects the combined effects of atmospheric radon progeny concentration, precipitation scavenging processes, and radionuclide deposition on the ground. Therefore, obtaining accurate gamma dose rate values is necessary to validate and calibrate models that aim to explain or predict dose rate enhancements associated with rainfall and radon dynamics. Understanding these variations is important not only for improving environmental radiation models, but also for distinguishing natural fluctuations in background radiation from potential anthropogenic radiological events.

Gamma radiation is continuously monitored at the Eastern North Atlantic (ENA) atmospheric observatory in the Azores archipelago in the northeastern Atlantic Ocean west of Portugal since 2015, together with other meteorological parameters such as: precipitation rate, temperature, relative humidity, atmospheric pressure, wind speed and direction, liquid water content and microphysical properties of the clouds, especially cloud height and depth. Radon concentration started to be measured at ENA station since September 2025 and the investigation of its influence on the increase of the ambient gamma dose rate is ongoing, together with the atmospheric stability classification, which will especially help to clarify its influence on the increase of the ambient gamma dose rate. Besides the continuous development of the model for gamma dose rate increase over the background, efforts were mainly focused on the development of various mathematical formalisms for calculation of the ambient gamma dose rate which is a physically meaningful quantity directly related to radiation exposure in the environment.

The ambient gamma dose equivalent rate ($H^*(10)$) was derived from count rate measurements obtained with a NaI(Tl) scintillation detector (Scionix), operating in the

energy range 475 keV to 3000 keV and auto-calibrated using a ^{137}Cs gamma source (662 keV), continuously monitoring the gamma radiation at ENA station. A theoretical formalism was developed to establish a conversion between the measured count rate (CPM) and the ambient dose equivalent rate, based on comparison with a reference Geiger–Müller (GM) detector (GM J305). For the reference instrument, a dose rate of 344 nSv/h corresponding to a measured count rate of 25 CPM, of which 12 CPM were attributed to internal background, yielding a net response of 13 CPM, was calculated. This corresponds to a conversion factor of approximately 26.5 nSv/h per CPM for the GM detector. The conversion factor for the NaI(Tl) detector was subsequently derived by accounting for its higher intrinsic detection efficiency and response characteristics relative to the GM tube, resulting in a value of 70 nSv/h per CPM. Owing to internal compensation of environmental and instrumental effects, the intrinsic background of the scintillation detector was considered negligible and no background subtraction was applied. The ambient dose equivalent rate was therefore calculated as $H^*(10) = 70 \text{ nSv/h per CPM}$. Given the energy-dependent response of the detector, the derived conversion factor represents an approximation valid for gamma fields with spectral characteristics similar to that of the calibration source or typical environmental radiation. The uncertainty associated with the conversion factor is estimated to be between 10 % and 20 %, leading to an overall uncertainty of approximately 20 % to 25 %.

Based on this formalism, the terrestrial background (BG) in the Azores was estimated for 2024 (Figure 1) and 2025 (Figure 2).

The estimated terrestrial BG in 2024 varied between 90 nSv/h and 96 nSv/h with an average of about 93 nSv/h (Figure 1) and in 2025 the variation of the BG was 86 nSv/h and

Figure 1: The estimated terrestrial BG at ENA station in 2024.

Figure 2: The estimated terrestrial BG at ENA station in 2025.

93 nSv/h with an average of 88 nSv/h (Figure 2). The model predicts that precipitation-induced washout of radon progeny leads to observable increases in ambient gamma dose rate. For intense rainfall events, the dose rate may increase up to about 16 nSv/h for 2024 (Figure 1) and 18 nSv/h for 2025 (Figure 2), whereas drizzle or weak precipitation typically produce increases of about 3 nSv/h to 4 nSv/h for 2024 (Figure 1) and 6 nSv/h for 2025 (Figure 2). These values highlight the strong influence of precipitation intensity on the efficiency of atmospheric radionuclide scavenging and subsequent surface deposition.

The long-term monitoring data indicate that the background gamma dose rate in the Azores exhibits only very slight interannual variability. This stability suggests that the natural sources contributing to the environmental gamma background, such as terrestrial radionuclides and cosmic radiation, remain relatively constant over time. Consequently, the short-term increases in gamma dose rate observed during precipitation events can be attributed primarily to the washout and surface deposition of radon progeny, rather than to changes in the baseline radiation field.

Another mathematical formalism to calculate the ambient gamma dose rate was undertaken for a high-purity germanium (HPGe) detector, owned by Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB) which soon will be operational at ENA station. The ambient dose equivalent rate $H^*(10)$ was derived from *in-situ* HPGe gamma ray spectra acquired at 1 m above ground level with a live time of 600 s. HPGe detectors provide high resolution gamma spectrometry that allows the identification of specific radionuclides contributing to the observed dose rate. By analysing CNF spectral files from the HPGe detector, we were able to quantify radionuclide activity concentrations and determine the corresponding gamma

dose rate contribution from radon progeny and other natural sources. The calibration was performed using four standard gamma sources: ^{152}Eu , ^{207}Bi , ^{133}Ba and ^{88}Y , which provide gamma lines over a wide energy range. For each photopeak, the efficiency was calculated using the source activity and the emission probabilities taken from the LNHB nuclear data tables (<http://www.lnhb.fr/home/nuclear-data/nuclear-data-table/>). The resulting efficiency points were then fitted to obtain the detector efficiency curve (Figure 3), which is later used to determine radionuclide activities from the environmental spectra. As expected, the efficiency decreases with increasing gamma energy due to the reduced interaction probability in the detector.

Figure 3: The absolute efficiency in energy for HPGe detector.

After determination of the detector efficiency, we fitted the efficiency function as $\epsilon(E) = 10^b E^a$ (with $a = -1.053$ and $b = -3.211$). Using the source activity and emission probabilities, the photon emission rate was calculated. Photon attenuation in aluminium and air was then considered to obtain the transmission factors. The resulting photon fluence was converted to air kerma and subsequently to the ambient dose equivalent H^* (10). Summing the contributions from all photon energies yielded a laboratory ambient dose equivalent rate of 77 nSv/h.

For the outdoor case, the main difference from the laboratory procedure is that the source is no longer a discrete calibrated source, but instead radionuclides distributed in the atmosphere and deposited on the ground (mainly radon progeny). Spectral data were processed within the calibrated energy range of 50 keV to 1.5 MeV, ensuring that detector efficiency was applied only where it is well-characterised. The measured dose rate, which inherently includes both terrestrial and cosmic contributions, was obtained by converting the net count rate to dose using the energy-dependent efficiency calibration.

To account for the missing high-energy terrestrial gamma contribution above 1.5 MeV, primarily associated with the ^{208}Tl line at 2.614 MeV, a constant high-energy correction factor (of about 1.10) was applied to the measured dose rate. This yields a corrected ambient dose rate representative of the full terrestrial gamma spectrum up to approximately 3 MeV, while still including the cosmic component. The cosmic contribution was treated separately and estimated based on site-specific conditions (altitude and latitude), allowing it to be subtracted in a later stage to isolate the terrestrial background. This approach ensures internal consistency across all time-resolved measurements and provides a robust and transferable methodology applicable to different geographic locations.

Practically, the same dosimetric formalism is applied in both cases. The main difference is that in the laboratory (indoor) the source activity and geometry are known, while for environmental measurements (outdoor) the radionuclides originate from atmospheric radon progeny and are distributed in the environment.

The calculations of the gamma dose rate and the terrestrial background (of about 83 nSv/h, Figure 4) based on observations provided by HPGe detector were then compared with the observations and the estimated terrestrial background provided by a spectrodosimeter (of about 80 nSv/h, Figure 5) for the same period (August 8, 2025 - September 9, 2025). The comparison shows a slight overestimation of the terrestrial BG by about 3 nSv/h to 4 nSv/h, which is probably due the fact that the HPGe detector may contain other materials like ^{29}Cu besides ^{13}Al , but only the latter was considered in calculations. In this case, the spectrodosimeter (RSS in Figure 5) was considered as a reference for gamma dose rate calculations based on spectra provided by HPGe detector.

Figure 4: Predicted ambient gamma dose and estimated terrestrial BG for HPGe detector.

Figure 5: Observed ambient gamma dose and estimated terrestrial BG for spectrodosimeter (RSS).

Continuous improvements of the model were undertaken in the meanwhile, which overall integrate cloud microphysics, radioactive decay, and precipitation scavenging processes to describe the observed increase in environmental gamma radiation during rainfall. The framework can therefore be used to interpret gamma monitoring data and to estimate radon progeny deposition during precipitation events. The results suggest that rainfall events can temporarily increase environmental gamma dose rates by enhancing the deposition of radon progeny. This effect should be considered when interpreting data from environmental radiation monitoring networks, particularly during prolonged precipitation periods.